

The COVID-19 2020 lockdown asserts traffic as a major source of benzene in Berlin, Germany – Supporting Information

Alexandre Caseiro¹, Seán Schmitz¹, and Erika von Schneidemesser¹

¹Research Institute for Sustainability, Potsdam, Germany

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Figure S1: Map showing the city of Berlin limits and the location of the monitoring sites and the meteorological stations.

Figure S2: Map showing the monitoring sites within the city of Berlin.

Figure S3: Performance metrics for the models developed for the urban background site (C_6H_6).

Figure S4: Performance metrics for the models developed for the traffic site (C_6H_6).

Figure S5: Performance metrics for the models developed for the urban background site (NO₂).

Figure S6: Performance metrics for the models developed for the traffic site (NO_2).

Figure S7: Time series showing measurements (train and test, C_6H_6) and data predicted by the selected model for the urban background site.

Figure S8: Distributions of the C_6H_6 test data and the concentrations predicted by the selected model for the urban background site.

Figure S9: Time series showing measurements (train and test, C_6H_6) and data predicted by the selected model for the traffic site.

Figure S10: Distributions of the C_6H_6 test data and the concentrations predicted by the selected model for the traffic site.

Figure S11: Time series showing measurements (train and test, NO₂) and data predicted by the selected model for the urban background site.

Figure S12: Distributions of the NO₂ test data and the concentrations predicted by the selected model for the urban background site.

Figure S13: Time series showing measurements (train and test, NO₂) and data predicted by the selected model for the traffic site.

Figure S14: Distributions of the NO₂ test data and the concentrations predicted by the selected model for the traffic site.